

Exploring Formulaic Language: Perspectives From Walter Ong and Daniel Dennett

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In this paper, I will discuss how formulaic language can be understood in the light of Walter Ong's theory of oral culture and Daniel Dennett's concept of memes. As empirical example, I use a corpus of almost 1 200 nationalistic songs from Norway, Sweden and Swedish-speaking Finland, registered in a total of 3 500 prints and reprints between 1770 and 1920.¹ These lyrics demonstrate the establishment and replication, in a Nordic context, of clichés still distinctly recognizable in contemporary nationalist discourse across the Western world. My case is thus the "formulaic language of nationalism", but the theoretical implications suggested are not confined to any particular genre.

Walter Ong: Formulaic Language as a Defining Trait of Oral Society

In Walter Ong's landmark study *Orality and Literacy* from 1982, the American scholar suggested that literacy brought on massive changes not only in the way humans express themselves, but in our very way of thinking. In the world we inhabit today, any thought can be given permanence by being written down. No matter how complex, ephemeral, or unorthodox an idea is, literacy means it can be preserved and used by others. In Ong's view, this is not the natural state of human communication. In oral societies – that is *all* societies before the advent of literacy – there is only one way to give permanence to your thoughts:

¹ The corpus was collected in 2004–2008 as part of the PhD project 'Patriotic Dreamlands: Music, Nationalism and Gender in the Long 19th Century'; published in Hanna Enefalk, "En patriotisk drömvärld: Musik, genus och nationalism under det långa 1800-talet" (PhD diss., Uppsala University, 2008). The number of individual lyrics is 1 196, the total number of songs registered is 3 593, since some songs were printed several times. Most of the material was found by trawling the collections of: Helsinki University Library, Finland; Kungliga biblioteket, Stockholm, Sweden; Nasjonalbiblioteket, Oslo, Norway; Norsk Musikk-samling, Oslo, Norway; Norsk Visearkiv, Oslo, Norway; Sibeliusakademins arkiv, Turku, Finland; Svenska litteratursällskapets i Finland samlingar, Helsinki, Finland; Musik- och teaterbiblioteket and Svenskt visarkiv, Stockholm, Sweden; Uppsala universitetsbibliotek, Uppsala, Sweden; and Åbo Akademis bibliotek, Turku, Finland. Although the corpus is large, it is by no means comprehensive. There are many more 19th-century nationalist songs.

Think memorable thoughts. In a primary oral culture, to solve effectively the problem of retaining and retrieving carefully articulated thought, you have to do your thinking in mnemonic patterns, shaped for ready oral recurrence. Your thought must come into being in heavily rhythmic, balanced patterns, in repetitions or antitheses, in alliterations and assonances, in epithetic and other formulaic expressions, in standard thematic settings (the assembly, the meal, the duel, the hero's "helper", and so on), in proverbs which are constantly heard by everyone so that they come to mind readily and which themselves are patterned for retention and ready recall, or in other mnemonic form.²

Walter Ong summed up and refined a field of enquiry which had emerged in the 1960s, with works such as Lévi-Strauss' *La pensée sauvage* and Goody & Watt's "The Consequences of Literacy".³ The view of orality and literacy as somewhat binary or even static entities – nicknamed the "Great Divide hypothesis" – was however challenged even before the publication of Ong's classic work.⁴ Some scholars put into question whether the shift from oral to scribal culture (or the shift from any dominant media to another) cause any fundamental changes in human cognition at all, and since the 1980s, research on orality and literacy has increasingly focused on oralities and literacies in the plural.⁵ Even so, few scholars question Ong's conclusion that that mnemonic strategies were a key condition for transfer of verbal information in pre-literate societies. Clichés and cultural common goods were tools that helped people to memorize information.

Ong's argument regarding oral culture and creativity is still quite compelling: In the typical oral culture, Ong claims, the objective was not to create something unique, original, or ground-breaking, but rather to employ and rearrange into new-yet-familiar constellations the shared, memorization-friendly cultural repertoire. However, later scholars have emphasized that traits such as these did not disappear with the

² Walter J. Ong, *Orality and Literacy* (London/New York: Methuen, 1987), 34.

³ Claude Lévi-Strauss, *La pensée sauvage* (Paris: Plon, 1962); Jack Goody and Ian Watt, "The Consequences of Literacy," *Comparative Studies in Society and History*, 5, no. 3 (1963): 304–345.

⁴ See e.g. Jack Goody, 1977, *The Domestication of the Savage Mind* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1977).

⁵ For examples of later applications and criticism of Walter Ong's theories, see e.g. Sibylle Schönborn, *Das Buch der Seele: Tagebuchliteratur zwischen Aufklärung und Kunstperiode* (Tübingen: Max Niemeyer Verlag, 1999); Adam Fox, 2000, *Oral and Literate Culture in Early Modern England 1500–1700* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2000); Paula McDowell, "Ong and the Concept of Orality," *Religion & Literature*, 44, no. 2 (summer 2012): 169–178; and Paula McDowell, *The Invention of the Oral: Print Commerce and Fugitive Voices in Eighteenth-Century Britain* (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2017).

advent of writing. As a historian specializing in 19th-century Scandinavia, I have found them in the literary culture of that time and place, and especially in genres given low status by the literary elite – children’s literature, pulp fiction, sentimental popular music, etc. The oral-society structures for thinking, communicating and memorizing identified by Ong clearly had a function in literary societies as well. The nature of this function can, I believe, be clarified by employing the concept of memes suggested by the American philosopher Daniel Dennett in 2006. But before delving into this subject, I would like to introduce my case: the genre of the “patriotic song” in Scandinavia, c. 1770–1920.

The Formulaic Language of Nationalism: The Case of Patriotic Songs in 19th-Century Scandinavia

The creation of a modern nationalist discourse gained momentum in the Nordic region during the first decades of the 19th century. There were early modern precursors in the shape of speeches, poems and songs expressing loyalty to the monarch, but the main influence came from the works penned by German intellectuals during the reaction against Napoleonic France. The German nationalism in the early 1800s became a significant source of inspiration as Nordic intellectuals sought to make sense of Scandinavia's new geopolitical landscape. During the upheaval of the Napoleonic wars, Finland was separated from the Swedish realm through Russian conquest in 1808–1809, and Norway, after centuries of subordination under Denmark, transitioned into a personal union with Sweden in 1814.⁶

One of the most important medias for the formation of nationalism in Scandinavia was vocal music. From the early 1800s and for more than a hundred years to come, thousands of so called *fosterländska sånger* (Sw.) or *fedrelandssanger* (No.) were written. They were performed in concerts, sung in homes and taught in schools. The genre attracted poets and composers ranging from the cream of the intellectual elite to village schoolmasters. During the few decades around the year 1800, the language of the nationalist song had solidified into a set vocabulary with a number of ready-to-use formulas. A qualitative analysis of the 1 200-song corpus mentioned above has identified thirteen key concepts: land/country, people, king/emperor,

⁶ These and the following research results are taken from Enefalk, “En patriotisk drömvärld”.

freedom, honour, manliness, mother, father/s, brothers, sons, blood, death, and God. In line with Walter Ong's list of memory techniques, many of these key concepts appeared together with a set of rhymes, forming a comprehensive brick box from which aspiring poets could pick and assemble a nationalist poem. (When analysing rhymes below, I will delimit the discussion to the Swedish language, with which I am most familiar.)

The first concept, "land/country" (also described as "realm", "soil" etc) is a given in the corpus of lyrics, since the criterium for including a song was that it mentions a (earthly) homeland. Onto this "land", the authors of nationalist songs attached a predictable range of adjectives – most commonly "beloved", "glorious", "beautiful", "free" and "ancient", although more imaginative ones also occur, such as the neologism "mountainous-high" of the Swedish national anthem.⁷ The "land" concept was even more user-friendly by rhyming (in Swedish) with "hand" and "shore", inducing scores of poets-to-be to write about a *land* whose *shores* will be defended by men with sword in *hand*, etc. "Soil" was similarly used together with its handy rhymes "word" and "North".

The concept of "people" is of course also pivotal in any nationalist discourse, if with Ernest Gellner we define nationalism as "a political principle, which holds that the political and the national unit should be congruent".⁸ However, "people" in the nationalist songs of 19th-century Scandinavia seldom referred to the entire population but only to the male half; sometimes only men capable of carrying arms. Not until around 1900 were women incorporated to some small extent.

At the beginning of the period, the monarch (the king in Sweden and Norway, the emperor in Finland after 1809) was acknowledged as the father and owner of the land. But even while praising the monarch fervently, the interests of "the people" were slowly but steadily advanced. Towards the end of the 19th century, the Swedish-Norwegian king was almost entirely elbowed out of the lyrics; in Finland, the Russian emperor kept his place as "the father of the country" for at least as long.

⁷ 'Du gamla, du fria, du fjällhöga nord' – the opening lines of the Swedish national anthem as sung from c. 1905. (In the original text from the 1840s, the wording was 'Du gamla, du friska, du fjällhöga nord'.)

⁸ Ernest Gellner, *Nations and Nationalism: New Perspectives on the Past* (Oxford: Blackwell, 1983), 1.

"People" (*folk*) does not have many rhyme words in Swedish apart from "interpreter" (*tolk*), unless you count *holk*, *dolk* and *smolk* ("birdhouse", "dagger" and "smudge", respectively). This caused many tortuous constructions in the line of "Sweden's flag, Sweden's honour, treasure of the past and interpreter of the future [...God] will support our free Swedish people".⁹ "King" rhymes with sing and young in Swedish, forming a very useful triplet of rhymes. (It also rhymes with *pung*, a word which can mean either [money-]bag or testicles. This rhyme was avoided.)

The "freedom" in the nationalist lyrics appeared in two senses: as the freedom of the nation (e.g. political autonomy) and as the right of the citizen to live his life freely under the protection of the law. In Norway, where the country's autonomy vis à vis Sweden rested on a set of laws from 1814, the two senses of freedom often merged. Of note is, that in all three countries – Sweden, Norway and Finland – the nationalist songs insisted that freedom had already been achieved. Freedom, then, should not be sought in social reform, but could only be maintained by close adherence to law and, if needed, by military action against foreign powers.

The definition of "freedom" remained virtually unchanged throughout the period investigated. The same goes for "honour". Honour figured almost exclusively in connection with warfare: the honour of the nationalist song is a soldier's honour. "Honour" conveniently rhymes with "swear" in Swedish, enabling the poets to come up with lines such as "Life and blood for Sweden's honour, faithful brothers swear hand in hand" (*Lif och blod för Sveriges ära, svära trogne bröder hand i hand*).¹⁰ Working with antitheses (another traits recognizable from Walter Ong's theory), the nationalist songs matched honour with "shame", which was used to describe military defeat and male refusal to fight.

This brings us to the sixth of the key concepts: manliness. The lyrics demonstrate an ongoing preoccupation with male virtues and their opposite: unmanliness. The core qualities of nationalist masculinity were strength and courage: "There is still manliness, courage and plucky men in old Sweden", as one of the most popular

⁹ 'Sveriges flagga, Sveriges ära, fornklenod och framtidstolk, Gud är med oss, Gud är med oss, Han skall bära stark vårt fria svenska folk' – the final lines out of K.G. Ossianniilsson's 'Sveriges flagga', published in 1916.

¹⁰ Final lines of "Studentsång" ("Dåne liksom åskan, bröder"), a translation from 1849 by Johan Jolin of the German song "Auf, ihr Brüder, laßt uns wallen" by Heinrich Weismann, 1838.

songs states.¹¹ The unmasculine man – the countertype, to use George Mosse's terminology¹² – is a man who does not fight. The authors of nationalist songs attacked this threat to national manhood vehemently: "May everyone carry a musket: only thus is Sweden's honour defended. Eternal shame on the weakling!"¹³ All in all, two thirds of the songs in the corpus contain references to manliness in one way or another. (The remaining third speaks only of "you" – the country – or of a "we" without specified gender.)

When women appeared in the nationalist songs, they were seen from an exclusively masculine point of view: as the soldier's reward, as sweethearts, wives or, sometimes, prostitutes. But although real women were sparse and summarily treated in the songs, the country as a mother was all the more prominent.

In the 18th century, the father and mother of the country were the king and the queen. But around 1800, the queen was no more described as the mother of the country – instead, the country itself became the mother. In the next step, the king was replaced by a ghostly collective: "the fathers", in plural. These were imagined as the dead warriors of an earlier, heroic age. Their "sons" were extolled to denounce the pleasantries of life to protect the "land of the fathers". To complicate the picture, the mother/country was sometimes described as simultaneously being a mother and a maid: the spouse of the fathers, but also the oedipal object of desire of the sons.

The "brothers" of the nationalist songs were usually brothers in arms. "Sisters" hardly ever appear in the corpus and "daughters" are even rarer. The task of the band of brothers was usually to die for their country – they were cannon fodder. Death often took the form of a sensual or even sexual experience in the nationalist songs. The weapon, or death itself, was described as a mistress; the battle as a marriage and the process of dying an "embrace": "The drum is sounding, Swedish brothers, the wedding hour of combat is here; The sword is flashing, the eyes are glowing, Death

¹¹ "Mandom, mod och morske män / finns i gamla Sverige än" – the opening line of "Mandom, mod och morske män" by R. Dybeck. *Vald samling af Student-Sånger* (Stockholm: J.L. Brudin, 1855), 116.

¹² George Mosse, *Nationalism and Sexuality: Respectability and Abnormal Sexuality in Modern Europe* (New York: Fertig, 1985).

¹³ 'Må en hvar musköten bära: så blott häfdas Sverges ära. Evig blygd åt veklingen!' *Bibliothek för quartett-sångare: Samling af 200 sånger för Fyra Mansröster af de flesta Svenska och Norska samt de bästa Utländska tonsättare* (Stockholm: Abr. Lundquist, 1867), song no. 131.

is standing in our ranks.”¹⁴ Sometimes the bride of this deadly wedding was the country, a mother who pressed her son to her bosom, making the metaphorical family of patriotic songs a dysfunctional family indeed. Also, the songs often promised eternal life to the fallen. Sometimes this promise was worded in a way that followed up the sexual metaphors used for describing death: the soldier, after having fallen during the “wedding” of battle, is re-erected in the form of a standing memorial monument; in Swedish *stod*, derived from *stå*, “stand” (cf. *stånd*, “erection”).

The word “stand” is in fact extremely common in the Swedish nationalist songs, rhyming, as it does, with a plethora of useful words: walk, beat, so, get, also, when, may, reach, blue (as in “our flag, yellow and blue”), and many more. By combining the land-hand-shore rhymes with the stand-rhymes and a few of the thirteen key concepts, almost anyone can write or even improvise a nationalist poem in Swedish.

A Matter of Memes?

The formulaic language of nationalism in the Scandinavian patriotic songs was remarkably tenacious. From the first songs about “honour”, “fathers”, “freedom” and manliness in the 18th century, the genre remained recognizably the same well into the 20th century. Not until the 1960s and 70s did the discourse (almost) disappear in Scandinavia. The language of northern honour, blood and soil had become distinctly unpalatable in light of the atrocities of the third Reich, and also, a number of comedians had turned the cheesy rhymes and the puffed up chauvinism into a laughing stock. In the last few years, however, words like “victory or death”, “honour”, “people”, “brothers” and “land” have once more started to reassemble themselves in the public debate.

Many scholars have probably encountered the phenomenon wherein concepts and symbols, even complex ones, appear to reproduce themselves as though inhabited by a will of their own. In discourse analysis and some lines of research in intellectual history, this has led scholars to paint a picture where the discourse (or the ideas, or the “spirit of the times”) seem to lead an autonomous existence outside of human control. Another attempt to explain and work analytically with this phenomenon is Actor Network Theory, where the objects and networks themselves are given

¹⁴ *Samling af Flerstemmige Mands-sange for større og mindre Sangforeninger*, vol. 7 (Christiania: Joh. D. Behrens, 1851), song no. 73.

agency. But shouldn't we ask why and how something abstract can take on the form of a historical actor?

A possible, even likely, answer to this question can be found in one of the oldest explanatory models of modern natural science: natural selection. For natural selection to function, three conditions are essentially required: individuals in a population must have the ability to reproduce, there must be variation within the population, and there must be various factors in the surrounding environment creating a selection pressure on the population (meaning that certain traits of individuals result in relatively higher reproductive success). This brings us to Daniel Dennett. In his book *Breaking the Spell* from 2006, he suggested that the conditions of evolution are also present in cultural phenomena. Instead of a population of individuals, we may think of a “population” of non-genetic elements. A language, a dance, a way of building boats – all are reproduced with slight variations, of which some are more suited to be reproduced in turn. Less sustainable and reproducible thoughts and habits are eliminated.¹⁵

With a term coined by biologist Richard Dawkins in 1976, Dennett called these cultural counterparts to genes “memes.” A successful meme, such as the Lord's Prayer or the multiplication table, is one that manages to stick with its human hosts and makes them reproduce the meme as faithfully as possible. Memes that are written down have an “evolutionary” advantage, as have those that have attached themselves to long-lasting organizations. If the meme is performed collectively, it is also a boon: individual misrenderings are automatically adjusted, and a faithful copy of the original meme is passed on to a large number of hosts. Of course, it is also advantageous for the spread if the meme is useful for its hosts (like the multiplication table or the habit of making streamlined boats). But one of Dennett's points is that even useless, parasitic memes can develop. A meme that presses the right mental buttons will be remembered even if it lacks function, and if it has also gained a foothold in a medium where it is automatically reproduced, success is a fact. Whether the fine-tuning of the meme has occurred by accident or been made by a consciously calculating originator is entirely irrelevant. The producer or reproducer does not need to understand the function or even the utility of the meme – if it has

¹⁵ Daniel Dennett, *Breaking the Spell: Religion as a Natural Phenomenon* (London: Penguin Books, 2007).

found its ultimate habitat, hosts will reproduce it.¹⁶ Since Dennett's book appeared in print, the digital world has of course provided ample illustrations of this, to the extent that "meme" today is almost synonymous to "internet joke".

In *Breaking the Spell*, Dennett never discussed the implication of his idea for historians and other scholars, probably because of personal lack of knowledge in the field. However, it is evident that, without mentioning Foucault, he has accidentally explained how discourses can appear so eerily autonomous, as if they had a life of their own. Neither did Dennett mention Walter Ong. Yet, whether he ever read *Orality and Literacy* or not, the factors that Dennett identified as beneficial for the formation of a meme are rather similar to the ones that Ong saw as crucial for the transfer of knowledge in oral cultures. It will seem that what Ong observed in oral societies was the workings of the memetic logic in a world without writing. When the written word appeared on the scene, these workings did not disappear but were just accompanied by another, yet more powerful, way of multiplying memes.

To return to the nationalist songs, I believe enough has already been said about them for their "memetic" properties to be apparent. Patriotic songwriters occasionally managed to produce formulas that stuck: words, rhymes and concepts, which accumulated in the genre. Moreover, the memes of nationalist song were backed by all conceivable mechanisms for faithful reproduction: performance in chorus, incorporation into a school system which caused rote learning in childhood, and dissemination through songbooks – a publication type where every new editor began their work by anxiously examining how previous song collections had been compiled. When Dawkins introduced the term in 1976, he did in fact point out songs as typical memes, and even exemplified with a song from a students' song book.¹⁷

To sum up, I propose that our understanding of formulaic language, not only within the realm of nationalist rhetoric but in a broader context, can be advanced by considering the mechanistic explanations put forth by Walter Ong and Daniel Dennett.

¹⁶ Richard Dawkins, *The Selfish Gene* (Oxford: Oxford Paperbacks, 1999), 189–201, including footnotes, and Dennett, *Breaking the Spell*, 78 and 341–357.

¹⁷ Dawkins, 1999 [1989/1976], p. 194.

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